

THE CONTENT OF THE COMPONENTS OF THE ORGANIZATIONAL AND MANAGERIAL COMPETENCE OF A MASTER'S STUDENT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8049663>

Abstract. *This article analyzes the content of the components of the organizational and managerial competence of a master's student. Organizational and managerial competence is considered as an integral professional and personal quality of a master student, manifested in his self-realization and characterizing the ability and willingness to independently organize his professional activities.*

Keywords: *organizational and managerial abilities, cognitive, activity, professional, components, personal, motivational, communicative, information and communication.*

In the process of forming the organizational and managerial abilities of undergraduates at the university, the teacher bears a great responsibility. Since the personality of each student undergoes changes in the process of forming abilities, the teacher needs to monitor the process of the emergence of personality neoplasms in the course of the formation of organizational and managerial abilities. To date, higher educational institutions have accumulated a certain experience in preparing a master's student in socio-cultural activities, and such experience is worthy of generalization and use in work.

Organizational and managerial competence is an integral personal characteristic that manifests itself in self-organization, reflecting the desire and ability to perform professional tasks in organizing and managing on the basis of acquired organizational, managerial knowledge and skills, and value orientations.

As V.A. Belikov notes, denoting the structure of organizational and managerial competencies formed among students, and the structure "...should be clear and logical so that the future specialist, receiving theoretical knowledge at a university, could be able to solve problems based on this knowledge..."[2]

In the structure of the professional competence of a master's student, as one of the key ones, many authors, including us, single out organizational and managerial competence. So S.G. Markovchin and S.A. Kravtsov understand organizational and managerial competence as "... an individual, integral, dynamically changing, relatively stable characteristic of a person, which is the result of his continuous professional and personal development and manifests itself in an independent and responsible solution of the tasks of ensuring optimal relationships"[4].

Thus, the organizational and managerial competence of master's students can be considered as an individual integrative and dynamically changing personal characteristic, which is the result of their continuous professional and personal development and reflects the desire, ability and motivational readiness to perform tasks of an organizational and managerial type, taking into account the acquired (developed) organizational and managerial knowledge, skills, as well as professionally important qualities and value orientations.

The study of modern approaches and works of a number of authors, which describe the structural construction of organizational and managerial competence, we came to the conclusion that the process of formation and development of a certain competence of the student is carried out through the use of a set of competencies, established taking into account the specifics of the educational organization and further professional activity graduate [7].

The organizational and managerial competence of a master's student is understood by us as a systemic psychological and personal characteristic, including the following fundamental components: cognitive, motivational, activity, design-research personal, designed to provide with the effective performance of organizational and managerial functions in the course of implementing high-tech production technologies. In modern conditions of development of innovative technologies, the problem of uninterrupted and reliable control is of particular relevance. First of all, this requires the formation of organizational and managerial competence of undergraduates in the process of their professional training. In turn, the promotion of this competence is ensured by the creation of the necessary pedagogical conditions, which we outlined in the study. This complex of pedagogical conditions represents those conditions, the provision of which leads to the successful promotion of its structural components.

For us, the most preferable analysis of the structure of the organizational and managerial competence of the student in the implementation of master's programs, proposed by E.V. Savenkova [5]. This structure includes a certain set of components: motivational-personal (motivational orientation), cognitive (experience recorded in knowledge), operational-activity (skills and possession of methods of activity in standard and non-standard situations) and communicative, allowing, taking into account the existing experience students in solving problems of a certain type of professional activity, to successfully put into practice the knowledge, skills and abilities acquired during the training.

As a result, in the structure of the organizational and managerial competence of a master's student, we have identified cognitive, activity, professional and personal, motivational, communicative and information and communication components.

First of all, the cognitive component identified in the structure of organizational and managerial competence allows, taking into account the experience of organizational and managerial activities of a master's student, to successfully implement in practice the knowledge gained in the learning process in a certain area of professional activity when solving problems of organizational and managerial types.

The activity component includes a certain set of organizational and managerial skills that are professionally important for a master's student and acquired (developed) both in the process of professional activity and in the learning process, allowing them to consciously and independently make informed management decisions.

The professional-personal component includes a set of certain professionally important qualities of a student that influence the qualitative characteristics of his future professional activity. Moreover, the professionally important qualities of a master's student are formed (develop) both in the process of carrying out his professional activities and in the course of professional education.

Since one of the distinguishing features of the professional activity of a student of a master's degree in management is its indispensable connection with the implementation of organizational and managerial activities, in this regard, the structure of his professionally important qualities

should provide the ability to manage subordinate units, as well as make informed management decisions in any situation [6].

An analysis of scientific research conducted in this area made it possible to identify a certain set of psychological and physiological professionally important qualities of undergraduate student, necessary for the implementation of his organizational and managerial activities.

These, in our opinion, include: purposefulness, determination, team leadership, sociability, non-standard thinking, the ability to make informed decisions in non-standard situations, taking into account the limited time resource, as well as in the presence of incomplete (inaccurate) information, the ability to self-reflection, the ability to act in conditions of significant physical and mental stress, etc.

Thus, the professional and personal component is characterized by the degree of formation (development) of professionally important qualities of organizational and managerial competence of a master's student (organizational, strong-willed, communicative and creative). An indicator of the adequacy of the development of competence in the professional and personal component is their qualitative manifestation in organizational and managerial activities.

The motivational component, in our opinion, is an important component of the organizational and managerial competence of a master's student and combines generally accepted, relevant and stable sets of motivational attitudes: motivation for the implementation of organizational and managerial activities and motivation for self-development as a manager (development of organizational and managerial competence) in the process learning [5].

In general, it determines the stability and nature of internal motives and attitudes that encourage a master's student to achieve a certain result in organizational and managerial activities.

Thus, the motivational component of the organizational and managerial competence of a master's student is determined by the degree of development of personal motivation aimed at achieving success in professional activities. The development of the motivational component of organizational and managerial competence of a master's student is determined by the opportunities and desire to develop their professional competence.

It should also be noted that the implementation of organizational and managerial activities is impossible without the formation (development) of the necessary level of communication, which is currently particularly relevant. Therefore, in the structure of the organizational and managerial competence of a manager, it is necessary to single out a communicative component that requires the application of sufficient efforts for its formation and development.

The communicative component of the organizational and managerial competence of a master's student is understood by us as a synthesis of knowledge, skills, constructive behavioral models and scenarios, values, as well as communicative qualities and experience of interpersonal interaction necessary to build effective communicative relations in the framework of organizational and managerial activities [5].

In addition, in order to solve problems of an organizational and managerial type, a master student must have the following communicative qualities [3]:

1) professional qualities: independent implementation of communicative activities, positive emotional attitude to the process of communicative activities, the ability to reasonably and competently defend one's point of view, purposefulness, adherence to principles, truthfulness;

2) emotional-volitional qualities: moderate perseverance, persuasion with a word, personal example, goodwill, sufficient exactingness, necessary self-control, objectivity;

3) general communicative qualities: sociability, social activity, initiative in decisions and actions, sufficient information content, self-confidence, resourcefulness, determination, ability to work in a team, rational self-criticism;

4) attitude towards people: honesty, openness, responsibility, decency, justice, courtesy, goodwill, trust, attentiveness, respect;

5) neuropsychic stability: balance, endurance, sensitivity, dynamism.

Thus, the success of the organizational and managerial activities of a master's student will largely depend on the skills and abilities to build emotional and value relationships that arise in the course of performing professional tasks.

It should also be noted that at present, taking into account the improvement of information and communication technologies (ICT), the issue of informatization of the main areas of society in general and the education system in particular is becoming quite relevant. Information and telecommunication technology refers to information processes and methods of working with information, carried out using computer technology and telecommunications.

In this regard, the process of formation (development) of master's students' skills and abilities in the use of modern ICT is of particular relevance. Therefore, in the structure of the organizational and managerial competence of the undergraduate, we can single out the information and communication component.

The information and communication component of the organizational and managerial competence of the undergraduate is understood by us as a synthesis of knowledge, skills and abilities of active information interaction in the conditions of the modern information environment (search, collection, analysis, systematization, translation, etc.), as well as the use of modern means of information and communication technologies in solving various problems of professional activity.

The information and communication component of the undergraduate's organizational and managerial competence presupposes the presence of two components: knowledge, which implies the possession of a certain set of theoretical knowledge in the field of information and communication technologies, and activity, which implies the presence of practical skills in carrying out organizational and managerial activities using information and communication technologies [1].

Thus, the presented components are manifested in the ability and readiness of a master's degree graduate to independently organize their professional activities, make informed management decisions, create conditions for the effective work of subordinate officials, competently use the system of organizational and managerial knowledge, skills and abilities formed in the learning process, and also successfully implement their personal qualities in the framework of achieving their goals.

The components identified in the structure of the undergraduate's organizational and managerial competence make it possible to link various competencies among themselves in the areas of training, as well as to determine the forms of development of each of the components within the framework of the formation of the graduate's competence model, which ultimately contributes to the development of organizational and managerial competence in general.

The specialist must have the basic competencies to solve organizational and managerial activities, research and analytical, scientific and pedagogical. The formation of special competencies provide training of specialists for specific objects and objects of labor for this area

and include, for example, socio-technological, socio-medical, social and legal, socio-pedagogical, socio-ecological, socio-psychological, socio-rehabilitation and others types of competencies for the implementation of professional activities by a social work specialist.

Based on the foregoing, we note that the process of professional training of a master's student at a university is a targeted training in theoretical aspects, the formation of professional knowledge, skills, and their development, consolidation through practice-oriented classes that enrich the student with personal experience.

The specificity of the master's program is that the student receives a deep theoretical training, acquires professional competence of a higher level. This program includes in-depth educational and research components, conducting research and scientific-pedagogical practices and writing a dissertation. A large number of hours are given to the master for independent work, which is extremely relevant on the way to becoming a master in his professional activity.

Thus, we note that university education should be based on motivating students to be true subjects of the educational process, since only personal work will allow a student to turn into a competitive, highly qualified specialist.

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